

Event metadata

Event title	WORKSHOP SERIES: Submitting sequencing data and genome assemblies to the European Nucleotide Archive
Event type	Series of workshops
Date of events	25 March - 2 April 2025
Time of event	1-4pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>The European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) is the European node of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC), providing a comprehensive record of the world's nucleotide sequencing information, covering raw sequencing data, sequence assembly information and functional annotation. The three INSDC members (ENA, NCBI-SRA and DDBJ-SRA) routinely exchange data which ensures nucleotide data is archived and shared across geographically dispersed locations (Europe, USA and Japan). The ENA is provided by EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute, EMBL-EBI.</p> <p>ENA team members Dr Joana Pauperio and Maira Ihsan will deliver a series of related workshops on submitting raw read sequencing, Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG), environmental DNA (eDNA) and genome assembly and annotation data to ENA.</p> <p>Each workshop will begin with an introduction to the ENA data and metadata model. You will then be guided through hands-on exercises using example data sets to practice data submission via one of three submission routes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interactive web-based submission: these are completed by filling out web forms in your browser and downloading template spreadsheets that can be completed off-line and uploaded to ENA. • Command-line based submission: Data submissions of this type are completed via the command line using ENA's bespoke Webin-CLI program. This validates your submissions entirely before you complete them, allowing you maximum control of the process. Webin-CLI is the only way to submit assembled genomes and transcriptomes. • Programmatic submission: these are completed by preparing your submissions as XML/JSON documents and either sending them to ENA using a program such as cURL or using ENA's Webin Portal. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 25 March 2025, 1 - 4 pm AEDT: Submitting raw read sequencing data using interactive web-based tools

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 26 March 2025, 1 - 4 pm AEDT: Submitting raw read sequencing data using programmatic tools ● 27 March 2025, 1 - 3 pm AEDT: Submitting raw-read sequencing data using command line based tools ● 31 March 2025, 1 - 4 pm AEDT: Submitting genome assembly and annotation data using the command line ● 1 April 2025, 1 - 4 pm AEDT: Submitting Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG) data to ENA and MGNify using the command line Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG) Command-line submission ● 2 April 2025, 1 - 4 pm AEDT: Submitting environmental DNA (eDNA) data
<p>Learning outcomes</p>	<p>By the end of each workshop you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify the importance of data sharing ● Outline the purpose of the ENA ● Explain the ENA Metadata Model and the importance of metadata ● Describe the data submission routes at the ENA ● Identify the range of tools and services offered by the ENA for data submission ● Submit the demonstrated data type using the ENA submission route shown in the workshop(s) you attend
<p>Format description</p>	<p>Hands-on workshops, online via Zoom. Participants could choose to join one or more sessions.</p> <p>Dr Joana Pauperio and Maira Ihsan led the training by introducing key concepts and demonstrating the steps involved in submitting data to ENA. Participants then had the chance to apply these skills in follow along activities.</p> <p>Questions were managed using a living (Google) document.</p> <p>Participation was subject to application with selection.</p> <p>Applications were reviewed by the organising committee.</p>
<p>Audience</p>	<p>This series of related workshops is for Australian-based life scientists and bioinformaticians who are working with nucleotide sequencing data and who would benefit from submitting their data to the INSDC.</p>
<p>Prerequisites</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Submitting raw read sequencing data using interactive web-based tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ None ● Submitting raw read sequencing data using programmatic tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ An understanding of XML and JSON file formats is recommended ○ (Optional) A basic understanding of how to interact with the command line ● Submitting raw-read sequencing data using command line based tools

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A basic understanding of how to interact with the command line is required ● Submitting genome assembly and annotation data using the command line <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A basic understanding of how to interact with the command line is required ● Submitting Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG) data to ENA and MGNify using the command line <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A basic understanding of how to interact with the command line is required ● Submitting environmental DNA (eDNA) data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A basic understanding of how to interact with the command line is required
<p>Technical requirements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A Google document (living document) was used to facilitate discussions. ● Access to the internet, speakers, a webcam, microphone and Zoom. ● Participants were provided with guest accounts to ENA's dev server <p>Additional software was required for some submission methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Submitting raw read sequencing data using interactive web-based tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Microsoft Excel or similar for editing spreadsheets ● Submitting raw read sequencing data using programmatic tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Notepad ++ or similar for editing XML/JSON files ○ (Optional) A terminal emulator (the in built option in Windows and Mac is sufficient) ● Submitting raw-read sequencing data using command line based tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A terminal emulator (the in built option in Windows and Mac is sufficient) ○ Java version 17 or newer ○ ENA latest Webin-CLI release ● Submitting genome assembly and annotation data using the command line <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A terminal emulator (the in built option in Windows and Mac is sufficient) ○ Java version 17 or newer ○ ENA latest Webin-CLI release ● Submitting Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG) data to ENA and MGNify using the command line <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A terminal emulator (the in built option in Windows and

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Mac is sufficient)<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Java version 17 or newer○ ENA latest Webin-CLI release● Submitting environmental DNA (eDNA) data<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ A terminal emulator (the in built option in Windows and Mac is sufficient)○ Java version 17 or newer○ ENA latest Webin-CLI release
Lead Trainers	<p>Dr Joana Pauperio, Biodiversity Curator, European Nucleotide Archive, EMBL-European Bioinformatics Institute</p> <p>Maira Ihsan, User Support Bioinformatician, European Nucleotide Archive, EMBL-European Bioinformatics Institute</p>
Training materials	<p>Each workshop in this series has:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Slides that introduce the ENA metadata model and provide an overview of the submission process and/or type of data that is the focus of the workshop.● A practical guide that provides step by step instructions on how to submit data <p>Submitting raw read sequencing data using interactive web-based tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Slides: ENA_submission_interactive_slides.pdf● Practical: ENA_submission_interactive_practical.pdf <p>Submitting raw read sequencing data using programmatic tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Slides: ENA_submission_programmatic_slides.pdf● Practical: ENA_submission_programmatic_practical.pdf <p>Submitting raw-read sequencing data using command line based tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Slides: ENA_submission_commandline_slides.pdf● Practical: ENA_submission_commandline_practical.pdf <p>Submitting genome assembly and annotation data using the command line</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Slides: ENA_submission_assemblies_annotations_slides.pdf● Practical: ENA_submission_assemblies_annotations_practical.pdf <p>Submitting Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG) data to ENA and MGNify using the command line Metagenome-Assembled Genome (MAG) Command-line submission</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Slides: ENA_submission_MAGs_slides.pdf● Practical: ENA_submission_MAGs_practical.pdf <p>Submitting environmental DNA (eDNA) data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Slides: ENA_submission_eDNA_slides.pdf● Practical: ENA_submission_eDNA_practical.pdf

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